

Madani: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin
Volume 2, Nomor 6, July 2024, Halaman 461-465
Licensed by CC BY-SA 4.0
E-ISSN: [2986-6340](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11670580)
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11670580>

Specification and English Tenses

Gilang Luthfie Dalimunthe¹, Ahmad Yudha Pratama², Nur Aini³, Dinda Salsa Sabillah⁴, Yani Lubis⁵

¹²³⁴⁵North Sumatra State Islamic University, Medan

Email: Gilangluthfie@gmail.com¹, pratamahmadyudha@gmail.com², rikaak02@gmail.com³,
salsabiladinda000@gmail.com⁴, yanilubis@uinsu.ac.id⁵

Abstract

The abstract in the English version must be written with fulfill the rules of good English writing for abstracts in scientific papers. The sentences in the abstract must be written in sentence type (tenses) are appropriate. Therefore, the researcher uses Report Text material specifically about student experiences, so there are four students who will be observed by the researcher. The research method used is a descriptive method or what is usually called a qualitative method. And qualitative data will be conveyed by observing students' handwriting. Based on the research results, it can be concluded that there are two types of tenses used in writing abstracts in English; simple present tense for writing "background" and "conclusion", and simple past tense for "goals", "methods", and "results". To minimize errors in using tenses, it would be better if each journal attached a file about the use of tenses in each abstract component.

Keywords : *English Specifications and Tenses*

Article Info

Received date: 30 May 2024

Revised date: 7 June 2024

Accepted date: 13 June 2024

INTRODUCTION

Learning English in Indonesia is still classified as a foreign language. This is different from other Asian countries that place English as a second language. Thus, learning English at various levels; from early childhood education to tertiary institutions in Indonesia, a lot of innovation is needed in terms of approaches, methods, techniques and learning media. More details can be found that difficulties in capturing foreign languages (listening) due to limited vocabulary, difficulty in conveying ideas in English (speaking) caused by difficulties in stringing words (vocabularies) and lack of understanding of English grammar structures and grammar, difficulty writing English sentences (writing) are caused by lack of reading (reading) so that the vocabulary is limited (Megawati, 2016). Educational innovation in the present context is related to technology in education. Technology in education is present in the world of education now as a scientific discipline that is concerned with the development and utilization of learning resources (Syahri, 2017). Rooyacker argues that the technology is used in learning and learning is expected to create a pleasant atmosphere for students (Klimova, 2015).

Even though language is something created by culture, if learning is not supported by attractive media it will fail. Learning English is the first foreign language taught in primary and secondary education institutions (Syahri, 2017). On the other hand, learning English in line with the 2013 curriculum is based on a scientific approach with characteristics centered on learning, including cognitive processes, providing opportunities for students to develop, finding knowledge through the learning process, learning from multi sources, encouraging students to be able to learn sustainably, build value and implement the principle that teachers, students and schools are a unity in learning (Ratnaningsih, 2017). The most basic thing that is needed by language learners is motivation and enthusiasm (Nan, Jianxi, & Dongmei, 2018).

Building enthusiasm for students must be through a course that is always new and interesting. The media that continues to be loved with a variety of novelty features in it is IT media. This IT-based learning media was created to serve the needs of teachers, students, educational policy makers and all individuals involved in education. The development of this learning media can come from YouTube (Lestari, 2016), social media like facebook, whatsapp, online magazine (Cakir, 2016). Among social media which is currently a trend one of them is whatsapp (Manan, 2017). Technology-based learning

media really provide solutions in improving the quality of learning English. So, 21st century learning framework requires every teaching and learning process to integrate aspects of technology to improve the quality of learning itself (Innovation, 2019).

English grammar and Indonesian grammar are different in some ways. One of differences can be seen in constructing sentences based on referring time. The difference of grammatical structure between English and Indonesian which will be learnt especially is tenses for verbal sentences because in verbal sentences the re will be shown the transformation of verb which does not occur in Indonesian structure. The patterns in tenses are considered as the complicate done by Indonesian students who do not have such a rule in their language, Indonesian. Tenses are the rule when we want to explain our activity and event in writing text. A study reported that punctuation mistakes were the most common errors committed by participants, followed by spelling mistakes, preposition mistakes, article mistakes, incorrect verb tenses, and incorrect word forms (Khatter, 2019). Tenses are a part of grammar. As we are academic students, we must have full understanding about tenses, because if we do not do it, there is much miscommunication that we get. But students do not have full understanding about this problem. They assume tenses as a big burden. We can find term "Error Analysis" in language. They see error could be very precious for us for teaching; there search that used the students' error on writing as resources to teach students. In Linguistics, according to J. Richard et al., (2002), an error is the use of a word, speech act or grammatical item in such a way it seems imperfect and significant of an incomplete learning.

Hendrickson (1987:357) mentioned that errors are 'signals' that indicate an actual learning process taking place and that the learner has not yet mastered or shown a well-structured competence in the target language. Learning tenses is important, because a sentence is constructed by using tenses. Even, now a days in elementary level, the students are taught not merely about vocabulary, but also they are taught how to construct sentence correctly. Besides, tenses mastery has contribution in learning English skills; speaking, reading, listening and writing.

Some students are not able to use correct tenses when they use English either spoken or written. They seem reluctant to use English, because they are afraid of making mistake. They think that the structure of English is difficult to apply, because it is quite different from Indonesian structure, including tenses. Although some consider tenses is complicated, but it must be learnt in order to use language appropriately and in the fact there are some students who have mastered tenses well. That becomes interesting to study how they learn tenses and what strategies they use. The students' errors are indicative both of the state of the learners' knowledge, and of the ways in which a second language is learned (Corder, 1967).

The notion of errors is different from mistakes in the sense of how they happen. Mistakes are considered as non-systematic and they may be caused by memory lapses, physical states, such as tiredness and psychological conditions such as strong emotion. These phenomena do not reflect a defect in our knowledge of our own language. Errors, in the other hand, are deemed as systematic since the errors committed by the users of the language reveal their underlying knowledge or competence of the language. Errors committed by the students learning. This study can show what strategies make learning tenses easier.

By knowing the strategies, the learners can master tenses in easy and effective way, so that there will be many learners who master tenses well and use English. When the learners do not know what strategies in learning tenses, they will keep thinking that learning tenses is difficult. As the result, they do not have mind to learn tenses and there are still difficulties in using English.

Tenses in English is related to the use of verb and adverb of time. An activity done in different time will use different tenses. It also applies in writing an English abstract. Another focus of the analysis of the abstract is the realizations of the tenses used. A study by Salager-Meyer (Nurhayati, 2017) reported that from medical abstracts had different verb tenses based on the functions like the past tense is used in purpose, method, result, and case presentation: while the present tense is used in data synthesis. However, in fact, the tense usage in abstracts is quite complicated as mentioned by (Swales, 2004) that even though the introduction and conclusion are often in the present tense, there seems to be considerable disciplinary and individual tense differences in sentences dealing with result. Magnum in his article adds that it's not always easy to decide which tense to use in arranging an abstract (Magnum, 2021). For example, if the research was performed in the past, some aspects need to be referred to using the present tense. Joshi who wrote an article about "using past and present tenses in

research writing” conveyed that although English has a complex system of tenses, simple present and simple past tense.

METHOD

In conducting this research, researchers used the Classroom Action Research method, PTK is action research carried out by teachers with the aim of improving the quality of learning implementation. This research will use four stages, namely: planning, action, observing, and reflection. This research was carried out by observation or directly in the field in order to master or seek information about tenses from lecturers who teach students. And information was also obtained from other journal articles. So that researchers can understand about tenses with their explanations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Learning tenses in English using the Drilling Method. Researchers must arrange the exercises from simple to complex, so that students can more easily understand new meanings and structures in English, especially in word forms. The simple present tense form can be taught in various ways, one of which is using the drilling method technique. The drilling method can help students understand patterns and formulas in the simple present tense. The researcher began practicing one of the structural objects included in the presentation. If the presentation is clear and students can understand the structure, they can repeat or make another sentence. After the presentation the teacher must choose a method that suits the structure. An example is the drilling method which can be used in teaching grammar. In its application, researchers took samples from the Uinsu campus environment which is currently implementing simple present tense learning. This research was conducted through two cycles. Each cycle consists of two meetings. The PTK design uses the Kurt Lewin model. This model contains four components, namely planning, action, observation and reflection.

1. Planning In this phase, researchers and collaborators make several plans based on the findings of the preliminary study. The aim of this phase is to develop students' understanding of using the simple present tense. Before implementing it, the researcher made the following plan: the researcher and observer discussed the steps that must be taken in this research and the researcher created activities for teaching and learning, such as: preparing a lesson plan based on indicators, preparing materials and topics, choosing the drilling method used in teaching simple present tense, preparing media to support the teaching and learning process, preparing observation forms, and then preparing test forms.
2. Action. a) Pre test The pre test is given at the beginning of the teaching and learning class before the drilling method is applied, by giving a test to determine their knowledge of simple present tense. The pre-test consists of five questions about simple present tense. b) Treatment Treatment was held twice a week for two weeks, twice in the control group and also twice in the experimental group. It is based on the PPP (Presentation, Practice and Production) technique. The treatment given can be seen in the lesson plan in the attachment and the PPP technique procedures (presentation, practice, production) used are as follows: a. The teacher gives a situation related to the topic b. The teacher gives a short dialogue to students c. The teacher asks several questions related to the dialogue, and models the correct answers which are then repeated by the students chorally and individually.
3. Observing In this phase, the researcher or lecturer writes and observes all activities that occur in class. In making observations, researchers used field notes to support the data. This is about the condition of the class and the student participants. Collecting data requires an observation or assessment format that is set accurately to carry out scenarios that act over time and their impact on the process of teaching and learning activities in the classroom.
4. Reflecting Reflection is a phase for processing data that researchers find when making observations. Evaluation is needed to carry out the next cycle to be achieved. This collaboration was carried out by researchers and teachers as observers. His participation in this section only helps the researcher to conduct and evaluate.

When lecturers teach tenses in English, especially in the form of simple present tense, without memorizing grammar rules, students can understand more easily. The lecturer also gives examples first related to these tenses. Some students became interested in the examples given by the lecturer, but there were also those who didn't seem to care.

Tenses are one of the fundamental elements in constructing grammatically correct sentences and conveying the time or circumstances of an event. Definition of Tenses : Tenses are a system used to express the time of an event or situation. In English, there are three main tenses known as present,

past, and future. Each of these times can be subdivided into different shapes to show more specific nuances of time. Function of Tenses : Tenses help the speaker or writer to arrange the time sequence of events that occur. By using tenses correctly, information can be conveyed clearly about when an event happened, is happening, or will happen. Main Tenses :

- Present Tense : Used to express events or circumstances that are happening at the moment ("I am writing").
- Past Tense : Used to express events or circumstances that occurred in the past ("She studied abroad last year").
- Future Tense : Used to express events or circumstances that will occur in the future ("They will arrive tomorrow").

Forms of Tenses : Every time (present, past, future) has several additional forms to express more specific nuances of time, such as present continuous (is happening), present perfect (has happened), past continuous (is happening in the past) , etc. Use of Tenses : The use of tenses in a sentence depends on the time context that you want to convey and the relationship between one event and another in the narrative or conversation. Difficulty in Tenses : One of the challenges in using tenses is choosing the right form to convey time accurately, especially in complex sentences or long narratives. Practice and Understanding : To understand and master the use of tenses well, practice in forming sentences with different tenses is very important. This helps reinforce understanding of how and when each tense is used. By understanding the basic concepts above, one can develop the ability to use tenses effectively in various communication contexts in English.

DISCUSSION

There are two types of tenses used in English abstracts, namely the simple present tense for all abstract components and a combination of simple present and past tense. There are 44 abstracts that use the present tense, and 57 abstracts that use a combination of simple present and past tense. This means that there are no definite requirements for using tenses in writing English abstracts in journals or scientific papers, even though, in writing English abstracts, you generally have to use the simple present tense to state facts and explain an event that actually happened.

During the discussion, he explained the results of research on the UINSU campus regarding learning tenses in English. Regarding the teaching and learning activities of English tenses at the Uinsu campus, specifically in class MP3 Satmbuk 23, the researcher followed the lecturer's method by giving examples first and then explaining the grammar slowly and as interestingly as possible so that it was easy for the students to understand. The researcher asked questions as an interview to their colleagues regarding what problems made them difficult in learning skills in grammar and also teaching methods and techniques. Most of the students said they didn't like English subjects because they didn't know the English vocabulary and grammar which required them to remember the rules and then do it before applying the drilling method.

The purpose of holding this pre-test is to find out how much understanding the students in class mpi 3 understand regarding tense lessons in English, especially the simple present tense material. Because the test results show the scores obtained, it can be concluded that the students' level of understanding is still relatively low. Post Test results were carried out after applying the drilling method. The researcher gave the task to the students to create one or more paragraphs using the simple present tense. So it can be seen that students' understanding is still a little poor regarding understanding tenses in English.

CONCLUSION

The use of tenses in writing English abstracts is very important. Different abstract components use different tenses. For background and conclusions, it is best to use the present tense (both simple present tense and present perfect tense). Because the components usually show statements, facts and implications of findings. Simple past tense also past perfect tense is applied in goals, methods, and results. Because the aspect tells of past events.

In addition, several tense errors were found in the data obtained. On the other hand, there are still errors in the use of present and past tense, as well as arranging English sentences with correct grammar, especially in writing English abstracts. Even though the content of scientific writing is in Indonesian, the English abstract plays an important role in the completeness of the article. Based on

the research findings, researchers advise reviewers to pay more attention to the use of tense in each abstract component.

REFERENCE

- Crystal, D. (1966). Specifications and English tenses. *Journal of Linguistics*, 2 (1), 1-34.
- Aliwear.(2012).BangAli Wear. Retrieved from: <https://alisadikinwear.wordpress.com/2012/07/07/mobile-learning-m-learning-solution-smartlearning-current/>.
- Magnum,J.(2021).UsingthePresentTenseandPastTenseWhenWritinganAbstract.MagnumProofreading Services.<https://www.magnumproofreading.com/post/using-the-present-tense-and-past-tense-when-writing-an-abstract>.
- Chalak,A.,&Norouzi,Z.(2013).RhetoricalMovesandVerbTenseinAbstracts:AComparativeAnalysisofAmericanandIranianAcademicWriting.InternationalJournalofLanguage Studies,7(4), 101–110.
- Nurhayati.(2017).VerbTenseAnalysisofResearchArticleAbstractsinAsianEflJournal.Progressive,XII(2), 57–63.
- Cokely, Dennis, and Charlotte Baker Shenk, *American Sign Language: A Teacher's Resource Text on Curriculum, Methods and Evaluation*, Washington: Gallaudet University Press, 1980.
- Crystal David, *A Dictionary of Linguistics & Phonetics*, Oxford: Blackwell Publishing, 2003, Fifth Edition.
- Dinsmore, J. (1981). *Tense choice and time specification in English*.
- Guenther, F. (1978). Time schemes, tense logic, and the analysis of English tenses. *Formal Semantics and Pragmatics for Natural Languages*. Dordrecht: D. Reidel Publishing Company, 201-222.
- Michaelis, L. A. (2020). Tense in English. *The handbook of English linguistics*, 163-181.
- Cowper, E. (1995). The features of tense in English. *Toronto working papers in linguistics*, 14.